

Dependency Treebanks

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Why?

- Linguistic research

- Corpus query

- Training tools (parsers) for NLP

- Downstream applications

Universal Dependencies

<http://universaldependencies.org/>

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- Milestones:

- 2014-04: EACL Göteborg, kick-off meeting
- 2014-10: UD guidelines version 1
- 2015-01: released 10 treebanks of **10** languages (UD 1.0)
- 2015-05: released 19 treebanks of **18** languages (UD 1.1)
- 2015-11: released 37 treebanks of **33** languages (UD 1.2)
- 2016-05: released 54 treebanks of **40** languages (UD 1.3)
- 2016-11: UD release 1.4, ~7 new languages
- 2016 fall: UD **guidelines version 2**

Goals and Requirements

- Cross-linguistically consistent grammatical annotation
- Support multilingual research and development in NLP
- Based on common usage and existing de facto standards
- Caveats:
 - Not a new linguistic theory – but linguistically informed and relevant
 - Not an ideal parsing representation – but useful for comparative evaluation
 - Not the ultimate annotation scheme but a lightweight **lingua franca**

Not
“**Universal**”
in the strictly
typological
sense!

Design Principles

- Dependency
 - Widely used in practical NLP systems
 - Available in treebanks for many languages
- Lexicalism
 - Basic annotation units are words – syntactic words
 - Words have morphological properties
 - Words enter into syntactic relations
- Recoverability
 - Transparent mapping from input text to word segmentation

Golden Rules

- Maximize parallelism
 - Don't annotate the same thing in different ways
 - Don't make different things look the same
- But don't overdo it
 - Don't annotate things that are not there
 - Balance: is it still the same thing?
 - Allow **language-specific** extensions

Part-of-Speech Tags

Open	Closed	Other
ADJ	ADP	PUNCT
ADV	AUX	SYM
INTJ	CONJ	X
NOUN	DET	
PROPN	NUM	
VERB	PART	
	PRON	
	SCONJ	

- Taxonomy of 17 universal part-of-speech tags, based on the Google Universal Tagset (Petrov et al., 2012)
- All languages use the same inventory, but not all tags have to be used by all languages

Features

Lexical	Inflectional / Nominal	Inflectional / Verbal
PronType	Gender	VerbForm
NumType	Animacy	Mood
Poss	Number	Tense
Reflex	Case	Aspect
	Definite	Voice
	Degree	Person
		Negative

- Standardized inventory of morphological features, based on Interset (Zeman, 2008)
- Languages select relevant features and can add language-specific features or values with documentation

Syntax

- Content words are related by dependency relations
- Function words attach to closest content word
- Punctuation attach to head of phrase or clause

Syntax

- Content words are related by dependency relations
- Function words attach to closest content word
- Punctuation attach to head of phrase

Not
"dependency"
in the strictly
syntactic
sense!

Dependency Relations

- Taxonomy of 40 universal grammatical relations, broadly attested in language typology (de Marneffe et al., 2014)
 - Language-specific **subtypes** may be added
- Organizing principles
 - Three types of structures: nominals, clauses, modifiers
 - **Core** arguments vs. other dependents (**not** arguments vs. adjuncts)

Dependents of Clausal Predicates

	Nominal	Clausal	Other
Core	nsubj nsubjpass dobj iobj	csubj csubjpass ccomp xcomp	
Non-Core	nmod vocative discourse expl	advcl	advmod neg aux auxpass cop mark punct

Dependents of Nominals

Nominal	Clausal	Other
nmod appos nummod	acl	amod det neg case

“Stanford-style” Coordination

- Coordinate structures are headed by the first conjunct
 - Subsequent conjuncts depend on it via the **conj** relation
 - Conjunctions depend on it via the **cc** relation
 - Punctuation marks depend on it via the **punct** relation

Multiword Expressions

Relation	Examples
mwe	<i>in spite of, as well as, ad hoc</i>
name	<i>Roger Bacon, New York</i>
compound	<i>phone book, four thousand, dress up</i>
goeswith	<i>notwith standing, with out</i>

- UD annotation does not permit “words with spaces”
 - Multiword expressions are analyzed using special relations
 - The **mwe**, **name** and **goeswith** relations are always head-initial
 - The **compound** relation reflects the internal structure

Other Relations

Relation	Explanation
parataxis	Loosely linked clauses of same rank
list	Lists without syntactic structure
remnant	Orphans in ellipsis linked to parallel elements
reparandum	Disfluency linked to (speech) repair
foreign	Elements within opaque stretches of code switching
dep	Unspecified dependency
root	Syntactically independent element of clause/phrase

Language-Specific Relations

- Language-specific relations are **subtypes** of universal relations added to capture important phenomena
- Subtyping permits us to “back off” to universal relations

Relation	Explanation
acl:relcl	Relative clause
compound:prt	Verb particle (<i>dress up</i>)
nmod:poss	Genitive nominal (<i>Mary 's book</i>)
nmod:agent	Agent in passive (<i>saved by the bell</i>)
cc:preconj	Preconjunction (<i>both ... and</i>)
det:predet	Predeterminer (<i>all those ...</i>)

Word Segmentation

- Must be **reproducible** on new data
- Surface tokens vs. syntactic words
- Chinese, Vietnamese etc.: no clues, non-trivial algorithm
- Arabic, Tamil etc.: part of morphological analysis
- Spanish, German etc.: rather limited cases of contractions
- Others: only punctuation (low-level tokenization)

Word Segmentation

- Fusions

- *al* = *a* + *el*
- *naň* = *na* + *něj*

- Clitics

- *vámonos* = *vamos* + *nos*
- *изменяться* = *изменять* + *ся*
- *potrafilibyšmy*
= *potrafil* + *by* + *jestešmy*

Where Are We Now?

- Two years of UD version 1
- 4 treebank releases (every 6 months)
- 54 (61) treebanks
- 40 (47) languages (over 50% world's population)
- Over 11M tokens; treebanks range from 1K to 1.5M
- Over 120 contributors
 - language group consistency SIGs
 - version 2 guidelines coming soon

47 Languages and Growing

▶		Ancient Greek-PROIEL	206K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Arabic	242K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Basque	121K	(LF)	📄	⚙️
▶		Bulgarian	156K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Buryat	5K	(L)	-	👤
▶		Catalan	530K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Chinese	123K	(F)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Coptic	4K	(L)	📄	👤
▶		Croatian	87K	(LF)	-	⚙️✓
▶		Czech	1,503K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Czech-CAC	493K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Czech-CLTT	35K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Danish	100K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Dutch	209K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Dutch-LassySmall	98K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		English	254K	(LF)	📄	👤
▶		English-ESL	97K	(L)	📄	👤
▶		English-LinES	82K		📄	⚙️✓
▶		Estonian	234K	(LF)	-	⚙️✓
▶		Faroese	119K	(F)	-	⚙️
▶		Finnish	181K	(LF)Ⓜ️	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Finnish-FTB	159K	(LF)	-	⚙️✓
▶		French	390K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Galician	138K	(L)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		German	293K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Gothic	56K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Greek	59K	(LF)	📄	⚙️
▶		Hebrew	115K	(F)	-	⚙️
▶		Hindi	351K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Hungarian	42K	(LF)	📄	👤
▶		Indonesian	121K		-	⚙️
▶		Irish	23K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Italian	252K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Japanese-KTC	267K	(L)	📄	⚙️
▶		Kazakh	4K	(L)	📄	👤
▶		Korean	-		-	-
▶		Latin	47K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Latin-ITTB	291K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Latin-PROIEL	165K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Latvian	20K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Norwegian	311K	(LF)	📄	⚙️
▶		Old Church Slavonic	57K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Persian	151K	(F)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Polish	83K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Portuguese	209K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Portuguese-BR	298K	(F)	-	⚙️
▶		Romanian	145K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Russian	99K	(F)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Russian-SynTagRus	1,032K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Sanskrit	1K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Slovenian	140K	(LF)	📄	⚙️
▶		Slovenian-SST	29K	(LF)	📄	👤
▶		Spanish	423K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Spanish-AnCora	547K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Swedish	96K	(LF)	📄	⚙️✓
▶		Swedish-LinES	79K		📄	⚙️✓
▶		Tamil	8K	(LF)	-	⚙️
▶		Turkish	56K	(LF)	📄	⚙️
▶		Ukrainian	-		-	⚙️✓
▶		Urdu	-		-	⚙️
▶		Uyghur	45K	(F)	-	⚙️
▶		Vietnamese	43K	(L)	-	⚙️

Where Are We Going?

- UD guidelines **version 2** coming soon
- Consistency checking

Common vocabulary is great ...

... because we finally
understand each other ...

... almost

*Childs of you be
vary acute!*

Consistency Checking

- Automatic tests catch only a fraction
- Focus groups on
 - Romance, Germanic, **Slavic**, Uralic, Turkic languages

Existing Slavic Treebanks

Language	Code	Treebank	Sent	Tok
Bulgarian	[bg]	BulTreeBank	13,221	196K
Church Slavonic	[cu]	PROIEL	7,818	72K
Croatian	[hr]	SETimes.HR	3,736	84K
Croatian	[hr]	HOBS	4,626	117K
Czech	[cs]	PDT	87,913	1504K
Czech	[cs]	CAC	24,709	494K
Polish	[pl]	IPI PAN	8,227	84K
Russian	[ru]	SynTagRus	59,130	1033K
Russian	[ru]	Google	5,030	99K
Slovak	[sk]	SNK	63,238	994K
Slovenian	[sl]	SSJ500K	27,829	500K
Slovenian	[sl]	SST	3,188	29K

Issues of Slavic Languages in UD

- Pronouns vs. determiners, numerals and quantifiers
- Attachment of cardinal numbers
- Verbs, participles, adjectives
- Core arguments
- Reflexive pronouns (clitics)
- Auxiliary verbs and modal verbs
- Comparative constructions

Pronouns and Determiners

- English + Romance languages: **DET** = article or pronominal adjective (*this, which, every*)
- We don't have this category! (Traditionally → PRON.)
- Some authors do recognize determiners in Slavic!

Pronouns and Determiners

- English + Romance languages: **DET** = article or pronominal adjective (*this, which, every*)
- We don't have this category! (Traditionally → PRON.)
- We have the words (except for articles).
- Currently functional borderline (but ellipsis?)
This.DET car is expensive.
This.PRON is expensive.
- Less strict in UD v2.

Pronouns Only

- Personal pronouns (including reflexives, but not possessives)
- Interrogative *who*, *what*
- Indefinite and negative derivatives
- Relative [cs] *jenž*
 - cs: *já, ty, on, my, vy, oni, se, kdo, co, někdo, něco, nikdo, nic*
 - sk: *ja, ty, on, my, vy, oni, sa, kto, čo, niekto, niečo, nikto, nič*
 - pl: *ja, ty, on, my, wy, oni, się, kto, co, ktoś, coś, nikt, nic*
 - ru: *я, ты, он, мы, вы, они, ся, кто, что, кто-нибудь, что-нибудь, никто, ничто*
 - sl: *jaz, ti, on, mi, vi, oni, se, kdo, kaj, nekdo, nekaj, nihče, nič*
 - hr: *ja, ti, on, mi, vi, oni, se, tko, što, neki, nešto, nitko, ništa*
 - bg: *аз, ти, ние, вие, се, кой, кое, някой, нещо, никой, нищо*
 - cu: *азъ, ты, мы, вы, и, са, кѣто, чѣто*

Possessives: Determiners

- If they occur without a noun ... **ellipsis**

*Můj otec je starší. Tvůj má ale více zkušeností.
My father is older. But yours is more experienced.*

- sl: *moj, tvoj, njegov, njen, najin, vajin, njun, naš, vaš, njihov, svoj*
- bg: *мој, твој, негов, неин, наш, ваш, техен, свој*
- cs: *můj, tvůj, jeho, její, náš, váš, jejich, svůj*
- sk: *môj, tvoj, jeho, jej, náš, váš, ich, svoj*
- ru: *мои, твои, наш, ваш, свои / его, ее, ею, их*

Both Possible?

- Demonstratives
 - cs: *ten, to, tento, tenhle, tamten, ...*
 - sl: *ta, to, tisti, oni, takšen, ...*
- Adjectival interrogatives/relatives, indefinites, negatives
 - *jaký, který, čí, nějaký, některý, něčí, každý, žádný*
 - *všechn, všichni, všechno*
- Relative pronouns **cannot** be explained by **ellipsis!**
 - *Muž, kterého *muže jsem vám představil.*
 - *The man, which *man I introduced to you.*

Issues of Slavic Languages in UD

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Quantified Noun Phrase

Quantified Noun Phrase

Quantified Noun Phrase

Quantified Noun Phrase

Pronominal Quantifiers

Language-Specific Labels

	Numeric	Pronominal
Noun governs	nummod	det:nummod
Numeral governs	nummod:gov	det:numgov

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Verb Forms

- Conflicting terminologies in traditional grammars
- Participle ... verb or adjective?
- Converb ... verb or adverb?
- Tags and features apply to **individual words!**

Verb Forms

- POS tags and features apply to individual words!
- *A ko **so se** leta 1942 **vračali**, ...*
 - past tense
- *... da ne **bi** v Atene **prišli** ...*
 - conditional mood
- *... v prihodnje ne **bodo vozili** zgolj les ...*
 - future tense

Verb Forms

- POS tags and features apply to individual words!

• *A ko **so se** leta 1942 **vračali**, ...*

Past???

Present tense

Participle

• *... da ne **bi** v Atene **prišli** ...*

Conditional mood

Participle

• *... v prihodnje ne **bodo vozili** zgolj les ...*

- future tense

Future

Participle

Verb Forms

- *vračali, prišli, vozili*
- [cs] “active participle” / “past tense”
- [ru] “past tense” / “finite!”
 - Active participle is something else: *нарушивший*
- [bg] “participle + past (aorist) / imperfect” (two subtypes)
- [cu] “participle + resultative aspect” (lang-spec)
- “I-participle”
 - But that would be a language-specific verb form.

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Core Arguments

- Easier cross-linguistically than argument-adjunct?
- **S**ubject of intransitive verb
- **A**gent of transitive verb
- **P**atient (direct object) of transitive verb

- Indirect object? Dative only?

Core vs. Oblique Dependents

- **Core arguments:** what exactly is it?
- English:
 - *He gave **John** the book.* (iobj)
 - *He gave the book **to John**.* (nmod)
- Spanish:
 - *Dio el libro **a John**.* (iobj)
- Czech:
 - Every Obj is translated to dobj, regardless the case and the presence of preposition

doj / iobj

- Not as easy as accusative vs. dative.
- Default: doj
- Heuristics for iobj
 - *Cením si vaší pomoci.* (Gen)
I appreciate your help.
 - *Čelíme velkým problémům.* (Dat)
We are facing big problems.
 - *Nedisponuje takovým rozpočtem.* (Ins)
He does not have such budget.
 - *Učí mou dceru fyziku.* (2 × Acc)
He teaches my daughter physics.

All Slavic Treebanks Have Non-Accusative “Direct” Objects

- *podrobit se testu; odpovídají smlouvě; jednat s někým*
- *mówi o niej; używa wielkich słów*
- *от которых зависит; относится к программам*
- *potrebuje informacij; slediti evropskim smernicam; ukvarjal se bom orožjem*
- *odriče se imuniteta; priključiti se naporima*
- *се характеризира с развитие; моля за внимание*

Reflexive Pronouns

- Direct or indirect object (dobj, iobj):
*Řízl **se** do prstu / Řízl **ho** do prstu.*
 - Including reciprocal usage:
*Políbili **se**. / They kissed **each other**.*
- Inherently reflexive verbs: ***smát se**, bát se / laugh, fear*
 - **expl:pv** (pronominal verb; previously compound)
- Reflexive passive:
To se snadněji řekne než udělá. / That is easier said than done.
 - **expl:pass** (previously auxpass:reflex)
- Impersonal construction (~ passive?):
Zde se mluví německy. / German is spoken here.
 - **expl:impers**

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- Comparative constructions

Modal Auxiliary in English

Modal Verb in Czech

Modal Adverb in Russian

Modal / Control Verb in English

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- Auxiliary verbs and modal verbs
- **Comparative constructions**

Comparative Constructions

Comparative Constructions

Wrapping Up

Wrapping Up

- UD has had a great start
- Still a long way to go. Consistency matters!
- Get involved. It's fun!

Děkuji!
Otázky?

Благодаря!
Въпроси?

Đakujem!
Otázky?

Благодаря!
Въпроси?

Thank you!
Questions?

Спасибо!
Вопросы?

Dziękuję!
Pytania?

Hvala!
Vprašanja?

Hvala!
Pitanja?

